

A Prospective Study on Managing Helicobacter pylori Infection: Enhancing Medication Adherence and Implementing Lifestyle Modifications

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ABSTRACT

Helicobacter pylori (H. pylori) is a gram-negative bacterium affecting nearly 50% of the global population and is a leading cause of chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease. Poor adherence to treatment regimens poses a major challenge to successful eradication, often leading to treatment failure and disease recurrence. This prospective study, conducted over six months in the gastroenterology department of Sagar Hospitals, Bengaluru, involved 152 patients who underwent gastroscopy. The primary aim was to identify barriers to medication adherence and improve the quality of life through pharmacist-led interventions. Key barriers identified included forgetfulness (86.2%), premature discontinuation upon feeling better (94.1%), side effects (91.4%), cost (7.2%), and lengthy treatment duration (88.8%). The implementation of structured counseling and patient education significantly improved adherence, with noncompletion rates decreasing from 45.4% to 2.6% and mean quality of life scores rising from 19.78 to 32.09. Identifying these key barriers offers valuable insights for improving medication adherence in H. pylori treatment. The study demonstrates that pharmacist-led counseling and targeted education are effective strategies in enhancing adherence, leading to better patient outcomes and quality of life. This approach can also serve as a model for managing other chronic conditions, underscoring the importance of addressing adherence barriers through tailored interventions.

Keywords:

H. pylori, medication adherence, pharmacist-led interventions, lifestyle modifications, prospective study.

INTRODUCTION

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) is a gram-negative, helical, and flagellated bacterium that colonizes the human stomach. Initially mischaracterized as a benign presence, its recognition as a significant pathogen followed the landmark discovery by Warren and Marshall in 1982, who demonstrated its role in chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease (PUD). Today, *H. pylori* is known as the primary cause of gastritis, duodenal and gastric ulcers, and is strongly linked to gastric cancer and mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) lymphoma. Its classification as a Group 1 carcinogen by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 1994 underscores its clinical importance.

Globally, *H. pylori* infects nearly 50% of the population, although its prevalence varies based on age, geography, socioeconomic status, and hygiene. In developed countries, improved sanitation has led to declining infection rates, while in many developing regions, the prevalence remains high—often exceeding 80%. The bacterium exhibits exceptional adaptability, including urease-mediated acid neutralization, flagellar motility, and the release of cytotoxins like CagA and VacA, facilitating colonization, immune evasion, and tissue damage.

Transmission of *H. pylori* occurs through multiple routes—fecal-oral, oral-oral, gastro-oral, contaminated water, and poorly handled food—making environmental and interpersonal hygiene key risk factors. The infection is typically acquired in childhood and may persist asymptotically for decades. However, when clinical manifestations appear, they often include dyspepsia, nausea, abdominal discomfort, bloating, or more severe complications such as gastrointestinal bleeding.

Diagnosing *H. pylori* infection can involve both invasive and non-invasive methods. Invasive diagnostics like endoscopy with biopsy allow for histology, culture, rapid urease testing (RUT), and molecular testing. Non-invasive tools include the urea breath test (UBT), stool antigen tests, and serology. Among these, the UBT is considered the gold standard due to its high sensitivity and specificity, though each method has its own limitations and contextual applications.

Treatment regimens for *H. pylori* are typically complex and include proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) combined with two or more antibiotics, such as amoxicillin, clarithromycin, metronidazole, tetracycline, or levofloxacin. However, antibiotic resistance, side effects, and the duration of therapy contribute to frequent treatment failures. First-line treatments often use standard triple therapy or bismuth-based quadruple therapy. In cases of failure, second- and third-line regimens involving rifabutin, furazolidone, or sequential therapy are considered. Probiotics are sometimes used adjunctively to reduce adverse effects and improve eradication rates.

One of the most significant challenges in successful *H. pylori* eradication is poor medication adherence, particularly in real-world settings. Factors such as regimen complexity, long treatment duration, adverse effects (e.g., nausea, diarrhoea), forgetfulness, financial constraints, and the misconception of stopping treatment when symptoms improve are major contributors to non-adherence. Non-adherence not only leads to treatment failure but also increases the risk of complications and the development of antibiotic-resistant strains.

To overcome these barriers, pharmacist-led interventions have shown promise. Clinical pharmacists can play a pivotal role in educating patients about the importance of completing therapy, managing side effects, and supporting behavioural changes through regular follow-ups and educational materials.

Tools like the Medication Adherence Rating Scale (MARS-5) can help identify adherence barriers and inform personalized interventions. Additionally, lifestyle modifications—such as avoiding alcohol, smoking cessation, stress management, and dietary adjustments—further support patient recovery and long-term gastrointestinal health.

This manuscript focuses on assessing medication adherence and quality of life among patients undergoing treatment for *H. pylori* infection. The study also explores barriers to adherence and the impact of pharmacist-led counseling, follow-up, and patient education using structured information leaflets. A multifaceted approach involving early identification of non-adherence, targeted patient support, and continuous monitoring is expected to enhance treatment outcomes and reduce relapse rates.

In an era where antibiotic resistance and recurrent infections remain critical healthcare concerns, improving medication adherence through clinical pharmacist involvement becomes essential. By addressing both medical and behavioral dimensions of *H. pylori* treatment, this research seeks to contribute to a more effective, patient-centered model of care.

METHODOLOGY

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design:

The study will be prospective study.

Study materials:

Participant information sheet, Patient consent form, Data collection form, MARS Questionnaire, QOL Questionnaire and Patient information leaflet

Source of data:

Patient's case sheet, Laboratory reports, Treatment charts and Patient interviews

Place of study:

Department of Gastroenterology, Sagar Hospital-Jayanagar, Bengaluru.

Study Period:

The study was conducted over a period of 6 months from April 2024 to September 2024.

Study criteria:

A. Inclusion criteria:

- All patient aged above 18 years
- Individuals who provided their informed consent to take part in the study

- Patients of both gender who undergo endoscopy and positive for rapid urease test

B. Exclusion criteria:

- Pregnancy and lactating women
- History of surgery or active bleeding in the upper gastrointestinal tract
- Known case of gastric cancer and mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue
- (MALT) lymphoma

Sample size calculation:

Procedure for calculation of sample size Two steps method i.e.

Step 1: Calculation of sample size for infinite population.

Step 2: Corrected sample size to required population.

- For infinite population

$$\text{Formula } ss = \frac{z^2 \times (p) \times (1-P)}{c^2}$$

SS = sample size

Z = Z value (1.96 for a 95% confidence level)

P = 43.9% = 0.439 (population proportion of H. pylori infection in 2022 is (43.9%))

C = 0.05%

Now after substitution of values in given formula, we will get 378.3

- Therefore, the sample size for infinite population (ss) is 378.
- So, sample size for required / finite population:

$$\text{Formula: - corrected ss} = \frac{ss}{1 + \left[\frac{ss-1}{pop} \right]}$$

pop = your survey's target population

Here, after substituting ss value (378) and pop i.e. targeted population which is nothing but 183 (1 patient/day for 6 months) to the given above formula, we will get 123.5

Therefore, corrected/adjusted sample size to required population is 123

Ethical Approval:

Ethical committee clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical committee of Sagar hospitals, Jayanagar, Bengaluru.

Study Procedure

This hospital-based prospective study was conducted over six months in the Department of Gastroenterology, Sagar Hospitals, Jayanagar, Bengaluru. A total of 152 patients with confirmed *H. pylori* infection were enrolled after obtaining informed consent. Patients not meeting the inclusion criteria or unwilling to participate were excluded.

Data were collected using a self-designed form incorporating information from patient records, lab reports, treatment charts, and direct interviews. Collected data included demographics, clinical history, diagnostic findings (OGD with positive Rapid Urease Test and biopsy), prescribed treatment regimens, dietary habits, and lifestyle factors.

Medication adherence was assessed using the validated MARS-5 scale, consisting of five items rated on a 5-point Likert scale (score range: 5–25). Higher scores indicated better adherence. Adherence was evaluated at baseline (Day 1) and followed up telephonically on Days 4, 7, 10, and 14, including counselling and documentation at each contact.

Quality of Life (QoL) was assessed at baseline and on Day 14 using a validated 10-item questionnaire (score range: 10–50), where higher scores reflected better QoL.

A Patient Information Leaflet (PIL) was distributed to support adherence and lifestyle modification. It was validated using Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio, translated into Kannada, and tested for readability (FRE and FK-GL). The layout and design were evaluated using the Baker Able Leaflet Design (BALD) Index.

Statistical methods:

The methodology utilized a range of statistical tools to analyse and interpret the collected data. Frequency and percentage tables provided a descriptive summary, while univariate data was presented using simple column and pie charts. For multivariate analysis, cluster column charts and box plots were employed. The chi-square test was used to evaluate statistical significance, with a 5% significance level and 80% power level applied throughout the analyses.

Statistical software:

Microsoft Excel was used to compile the data and SPSS version 27 was used to analyse the data.

RESULTS

i) Demographics

Table No.01 Distribution of the study participants according to gender (N=152)

GENDER	Frequency (n)	Percent(%)
Female	69	45.4
Male	83	54.6
Total	152	100.0

A total of 152 patients participated in this study, with a majority of 54.6% (83) being male and 45.4% (69) being female.

Table No.2: Distribution of the study participants according to age (N=152)

Age Interval	Frequency(n)	Percent
<30 years	9	5.9
30-59 years	67	44.1
>60 years	76	50.0
Total	152	100.0

The majority of participants, 50% (76), were under 60 years old, while 44.1% (67) were between 30 and 59 years old, and 5.9% (9) were under 30 years old.

ii) Medication adherence (barriers)

Table No.03: Barriers to medication adherence in baseline

Assessment	Base line	
	Frequency	Percent
Forgetfulness	131	86.2
Feel Better	143	94.1
Due to Side Effects	139	91.4
Cost Issue	11	7.2
Long Duration	135	88.8

The table no. 3 summarizes baseline assessment of barriers to medication adherence. Among patients, 86.2% (131) reported forgetfulness as a barrier, 94.1% (143) stopped treatment because they felt better, 91.4% (139) cited side effects, 7.2% (11) mentioned cost issues, and 88.8% (135) pointed to the long duration of treatment as a barrier to adherence.

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Table No.04 I forget to take my H. pylori medication as prescribed?

Options	Baseline (day 1)		1 st Follow-up (day 4)		2 nd Follow-up (day 7)		3 rd Follow-up (day 10)		4 th Follow-up (day 14)	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Always	14	9.2	10	6.6	6	3.9	8	5.3	0	0
Often	32	21.1	26	17.1	18	11.8	24	15.8	14	9.2
Sometimes	39	25.7	36	23.7	43	28.3	41	27.0	40	26.3
Rarely	46	30.3	54	35.5	56	36.8	51	33.6	58	38.1
Never	21	13.8	26	17.1	29	19.1	28	18.4	40	26.3
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0%	152	100.0
Friedman test applied, chi-square statistic = 179.668, p-value<0.001										

The table no. 4 presents responses to the statement "I forget to take my H. pylori medication as prescribed" across five time points. At Baseline, 9.2% (14) selected "Always," while 21.1% (32) chose "Often," and 25.7% (39) indicated "Sometimes." By the 1st Follow-up, "Always" decreased to 6.6% (10), and "Often" to 17.1% (26). The 2nd Follow-up saw "Sometimes" rise to 28.3% (43), with "Rarely" increasing to 36.8% (56). By the 3rd Follow-up, "Rarely" reached 33.6% (51), and "Never" rose to 18.4% (28) in the 4th Follow-up, indicating a trend toward improved adherence over time.

Table No.05 I stop taking my H. pylori medication when I feel better?

Options	Baseline (day 1)		1 st Follow-up (day 4)		2 nd Follow-up (day 7)		3 rd Follow-up (day 10)		4 th Follow-up (day 14)	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Always	36	23.7	28	18.4	24	15.8	18	11.8	2	1.3
Often	36	23.7	32	21.1	30	19.7	25	16.4	13	8.5
Sometimes	35	23.0	41	27.0	42	27.6	46	30.3	38	25
Rarely	36	23.7	35	23.0	46	30.3	49	32.2	51	33.5
Never	9	5.9	16	10.5	10	6.6	14	9.2	48	31.5
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0

Friedman test applied, chi-square statistic = 132.628, p-value<0.001

The table no.5 shows outlines responses to the statement "I stop taking my H. pylori medication when I feel better?" over five assessment points. At Baseline, 23.7% (36) selected "Always," while 23.0% (35) chose "Sometimes." By the 1st Follow-up, "Always" decreased to 18.4% (28) and "Often" remained stable at 21.1% (32). The 2nd Follow-up indicated an increase in "Sometimes" to 27.6% (42), while "Rarely" rose to 30.3% (46). By the 4th Follow-up, "Never" saw a significant increase to 31.5% (48), highlighting an overall trend towards better medication adherence over time.

Table No.06 I avoid taking my H. pylori medication due to side effects?

Options	Baseline (day 1)		1 st Follow-up (day 4)		2 nd Follow-up (day 7)		3 rd Follow-up (day 10)		4 th Follow-up (day 14)	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Always	37	24.3	25	16.4	21	13.8	15	9.9	0	0
Often	44	28.9	40	26.3	36	23.7	30	19.7	19	12.5
Sometimes	29	19.1	38	25.0	42	27.6	44	28.9	45	29.6
Rarely	29	19.1	35	23.0	40	26.3	50	32.9	52	34.2
Never	13	8.6	14	9.2	13	8.6	13	8.6	36	23.6
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0
Friedman test applied, chi-square statistic = 73.242, p-value<0.001										

The table no.6 presents responses to the statement "I avoid taking my H. pylori medication due to side effects?" across five assessment points. At Baseline, 24.3% (37) reported "Always," while 28.9% (44) selected "Often." By the 1st Follow-up, "Always" decreased to 16.4% (25) and "Often" to 26.3% (40). The 2nd Follow-up showed an increase in "Sometimes" to 27.6% (42) and "Rarely" to 26.3% (40). By the 4th Follow-up, "Never" significantly increased to 23.6% (36), indicating improved medication adherence over time

Table No.07 The cost of my H. pylori medication affects how consistently I take it?

Options	Baseline (day 1)		1 st Follow-up (day 4)		2 nd Follow-up (day 7)		3 rd Follow-up (day 10)		4 th Follow-up (day 14)	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Always	49	32.2	18	11.8	14	9.2	7	4.6	0	0
Often	40	26.3	38	19.7	36	23.7	20	13.2	3	1.9
Sometimes	34	22.4	48	31.6	50	32.9	52	34.2	16	10.5
Rarely	22	14.5	36	23.7	40	26.3	45	29.6	41	26.9
Never	7	4.6	20	13.2	12	7.9	28	18.4	50	32.8
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0

Friedman test applied, chi-square statistic = 82.729, p-value<0.001

The table no.7 summarizes responses to the statement "The cost of my H. pylori medication affects how consistently I take it?" across five follow-up assessments. Initially, at Baseline, 32.2% (49) reported "Always," while 26.3% (40) chose "Often." However, by the 1st Follow-up, "Always" decreased to 11.8% (18) and "Often" to 19.7% (38). The 2nd Follow-up saw an increase in "Sometimes" to 32.9% (50) and "Rarely" to 26.3% (40). Notably, "Never" rose significantly to 32.8% (50) by the 4th Follow-up, indicating improved adherence. The Friedman test revealed a statistically significant change in responses (chi-square statistic = 82.729, p-value < 0.001).

Table No.08 The long duration of the H. pylori treatment affects my adherence to the regimen?

Options	Baseline (day 1)		1 st Follow-up (day 4)		2 nd Follow-up (day 7)		3 rd Follow-up (day 10)		4 th Follow-up (day 14)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Always	44	28.9	28	18.4	24	15.8	8	5.3	4	2.6
Often	44	28.9	38	25.0	36	23.7	30	19.7	25	16.4
Sometimes	27	17.8	40	26.3	42	27.6	43	28.3	45	29.6
Rarely	20	13.2	30	19.7	34	22.4	45	29.6	47	30.9
Never	17	11.2	16	10.5	14	9.2	26	17.1	31	20.3
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0	152	100.0
Friedman test applied, chi-square statistic = 82.729, p-value<0.001										

The table no.8 displays responses to the question "The long duration of H. pylori affects my adherence to the regimen?" over five assessment points. At Baseline, 28.9% (44) reported "Always," and this decreased to 18.4% (28) at the 1st Follow-up. "Often" responses remained relatively stable, starting at 28.9% (44) and decreasing slightly to 25.0% (38) by the 1st Follow-up. "Sometimes" increased from 17.8% (27) to 26.3% (40) in the 1st Follow-up, peaking at 29.6% (45) by the 4th Follow-up. The "Never" responses showed a notable increase from 11.2% (17) at Baseline to 20.3% (31) by the 4th Follow-up, indicating a trend toward improved adherence over time.

iii) Quality of life

Table No.09: Did you complete the full course of antibiotics for your H. pylori treatment as prescribed?

QOL options	BASELINE (day 1)		FOLLOW UP (day 14)	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Not at all	69	45.4	4	2.6
Slightly	59	38.8	35	23.0
Moderately	19	12.5	57	37.5
Quite a bit	5	3.3	46	30.3
Completely	0	0.0	10	6.6
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0

The table no.9 compares baseline (day 1) and follow-up (day 14) responses for QOL item 1. On day 1, 45.4% (69) of patients reported "Not at all," 38.8% (59) reported "Slightly," and 12.5% (19) reported "Moderately." By day 14, only 2.6% (4) reported "Not at all," while 37.5% (57) reported "Moderately," and 30.3% (46) reported "Quite a bit." Additionally, 6.6% (10) reported "Completely" on day 14, whereas no patients (0.0%) reported this at baseline.

Table No.10 In the past two weeks, did you miss any doses of your medication?

QOL options	BASELINE (day 1)		FOLLOW UP (day 14)	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Not at all	50	32.9	6	3.9
Slightly	60	39.5	30	19.7
Moderately	34	22.4	56	36.8
Quite a bit	8	5.3	52	34.2
Completely	0	0.0	8	5.3
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0

The table no.10 compares baseline (day 1) and follow-up (day 14) responses for QOL item 2. On day 1, 32.9% (50) of patients reported "Not at all," 39.5% (60) reported "Slightly," and 22.4% (34) reported "Moderately." By day 14, only 3.9% (6) reported "Not at all," while 36.8% (56) reported "Moderately," and 34.2% (52) reported "Quite a bit."

Table No.11 Did you experience any side effects or issues that made it difficult to adhere to the medication regimen?

QOL	BASELINE (day 1)		FOLLOW UP (day 14)	
options	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Not at all	59	38.8	5	3.3
Slightly	59	38.8	34	22.4
Moderately	29	19.1	58	38.2
Quite a bit	5	3.3	41	27.0
Completely	0	0.0	14	9.2
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0

The table no.11 compares baseline (day 1) and follow-up (day 14) responses for QOL item 3. On day 1, 38.8% (59) of patients reported "Not at all," 38.8% (59) reported "Slightly," and 19.1% (29) reported "Moderately." By day 14, only 3.3% (5) reported "Not at all," while 38.2% (58) reported "Moderately," and 27.0% (41) reported "Quite a bit." Additionally, 9.2% (14) reported "Completely" on day 14, whereas no patients (0.0%) reported this at baseline.

Table No.12 Do you feel that the combination of lifestyle changes and medication has helped improve your condition?

QOL	BASELINE (day 1)		FOLLOW UP (day 14)	
options	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Not at all	45	29.6	3	2.0
Slightly	52	34.2	33	21.7
Moderately	46	30.3	55	36.2
Quite a bit	9	5.9	40	26.3
Completely	0	0.0	21	13.8
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0

The table no.12 compares baseline (day 1) and follow-up (day 14) responses for QOL item 4. On day 1, 29.6% (45) of patients reported "Not at all," 34.2% (52) reported "Slightly," and 30.3% (46) reported "Moderately." By day 14, only 2.0% (3) reported "Not at all," while 36.2% (55) reported "Moderately," and 26.3% (40) reported "Quite a bit." Additionally, 13.8% (21) reported "Completely" on day 14, whereas no patients (0.0%) reported this at baseline.

Table No.13 Did you make any dietary changes as recommended (e.g., avoiding certain foods or drinks)?

QOL	BASELINE (day 1)		FOLLOW UP (day 14)	
	options	Frequency	Percent	Frequency
Not at all	36	23.7	5	3.3
Slightly	63	41.4	37	24.3
Moderately	47	30.9	54	35.5
Quite a bit	6	3.9	43	28.3
Completely	0	0.0	13	8.6
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0

The table no.13 compares baseline (day 1) and follow-up (day 14) responses for QOL item 5. On day 1, 23.7% (36) of patients reported "Not at all," 41.4% (63) reported "Slightly," and 30.9% (47) reported "Moderately." By day 14, only 3.3% (5) reported "Not at all," while 35.5% (54) reported "Moderately," and 28.3% (43) reported "Quite a bit." Additionally, 8.6% (13) reported "Completely" on day 14, whereas no patients (0.0%)

Table No.14 Did you successfully avoid alcohol, smoking, or other risk factors during the past two weeks?

QOL	BASELINE (day 1)		FOLLOW UP (day 14)	
	options	Frequency	Percent	Frequency
Not at all	37	24.3	6	3.9
Slightly	64	42.1	26	17.1
Moderately	46	30.3	58	38.2
Quite a bit	4	2.6	47	30.9
Completely	1	.7	15	9.9
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0

The table no.14 compares baseline (day 1) and follow-up (day 14) responses for QOL item 6. On day 1, 24.3% (37) of patients reported "Not at all," 42.1% (64) reported "Slightly," and 30.3% (46) reported "Moderately." By day 14, only 3.9% (6) reported "Not at all," while 38.2% (58) reported "Moderately," and 30.9% (47) reported "Quite a bit." Additionally, 9.9% (15) reported "Completely" on day 14, compared to 0.7% (1) at baseline.

Table No.15: Have you implemented any stress management strategies (e.g., relaxation techniques, exercise) as part of your lifestyle modifications?

QOL	BASELINE (day 1)		FOLLOW UP (day 14)	
options	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Not at all	52	34.2	6	3.9
Slightly	55	36.2	28	18.4
Moderately	33	21.7	63	41.4
Quite a bit	12	7.9	40	26.3
Completely	0	0.0	15	9.9
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0

The table no.15 compares baseline (day 1) and follow-up (day 14) responses for QOL item 7. On day 1, 34.2% (52) of patients reported "Not at all," 36.2% (55) reported "Slightly," and 21.7% (33) reported "Moderately." By day 14, only 3.9% (6) reported "Not at all," while 41.4% (63) reported "Moderately," and 26.3% (40) reported "Quite a bit." Additionally, 9.9% (15) reported "Completely" on day 14, whereas no patients (0.0%)

Table No.16 Have you noticed an improvement in your symptoms as a result of lifestyle changes (e.g., dietary adjustments, stress reduction)?

QOL	BASELINE (day 1)		FOLLOW UP (day 14)	
options	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Not at all	59	38.8	2	1.3
Slightly	53	34.9	38	25.0
Moderately	35	23.0	58	38.2
Quite a bit	5	3.3	47	30.9
Completely	0	0.0	7	4.6
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0

The table no.16 compares baseline (day 1) and follow-up (day 14) responses for QOL item 8. On day 1, 38.8% (59) of patients reported "Not at all," 34.9% (53) reported "Slightly," and 23.0% (35) reported "Moderately." By day 14, only 1.3% (2) reported "Not at all," while 38.2% (58) reported "Moderately," and 30.9% (47) reported "Quite a bit." Additionally, 4.6% (7) reported "Completely" on day 14, whereas no patients (0.0%) reported this at baseline.

Table No.17 Are you satisfied with the changes you've made in your lifestyle along with your H. pylori treatment?

QOL	BASELINE (day 1)		FOLLOW UP (day 14)	
options	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Not at all	56	36.8	6	3.9
Slightly	55	36.2	28	18.4
Moderately	37	24.3	66	43.4
Quite a bit	4	2.6	42	27.6
Completely	0	0.0	10	6.6
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0

The table no.17 compares baseline (day 1) and follow-up (day 14) responses for QOL item 9. On day 1, 36.8% (56) of patients reported "Not at all," 36.2% (55) reported "Slightly," and 24.3% (37) reported "Moderately." By day 14, only 3.9% (6) reported "Not at all," while 43.4% (66) reported "Moderately," and 27.6% (42) reported "Quite a bit." Additionally, 6.6% (10) reported "Completely" on day 14, whereas no patients (0.0%)

Table No.18 How would you rate your overall quality of life after following the prescribed medication and lifestyle changes?

QOL	BASELINE (day 1)		FOLLOW UP (day 14)	
options	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Very poor	47	30.9	6	3.9
Poor	76	50.0	23	15.1
Neutral	27	17.8	40	26.3
Good	2	1.3	62	40.8
Excellent	0	0.0	21	13.8
Total	152	100.0	152	100.0

The table no.18 and figure no.25 shows QOL item 10 responses at baseline and follow-up. On day 1, 30.9% (47) rated their quality of life as "Very poor," 50.0% (76) as "Poor," and 17.8% (27) as "Neutral." By day 14, only 3.9% (6) rated it as "Very poor," 15.1% (23) as "Poor," and 26.3% (40) as "Neutral." Meanwhile, 40.8% (62) rated it as "Good," and 13.8% (21) as "Excellent."

Table No.19 The mean quality of life score assessed between baseline and follow-up.

QOL Assessment	Mean	Std. Deviation	Min	Max	Percentiles			Significance
					25th	50th (Median)	75th	
ITEM1 BASELINE	1.74	.803	1	4	1.00	2.00	2.00	P<0.001
ITEM1 FOLLOW UP	3.15	.940	1	5	2.00	3.00	4.00	
ITEM2 BASELINE	2.00	.876	1	4	1.00	2.00	3.00	P<0.001
ITEM2 FOLLOW UP	3.17	.940	1	5	3.00	3.00	4.00	
ITEM3 BASELINE	1.87	.835	1	4	1.00	2.00	2.00	P<0.001
ITEM3 FOLLOW UP	3.16	.986	1	5	2.00	3.00	4.00	
ITEM4 BASELINE	2.12	.908	1	4	1.00	2.00	3.00	P<0.001
ITEM4 FOLLOW UP	3.28	1.019	1	5	3.00	3.00	4.00	
ITEM5 BASELINE	2.15	.828	1	4	2.00	2.00	3.00	P<0.001
ITEM5 FOLLOW UP	3.14	.993	1	5	2.00	3.00	4.00	
ITEM6 BASELINE	2.13	.835	1	5	2.00	2.00	3.00	P<0.001
ITEM6 FOLLOW UP	3.26	.987	1	5	3.00	3.00	4.00	
ITEM7 BASELINE	2.03	.938	1	4	1.00	2.00	3.00	P<0.001
ITEM7 FOLLOW UP	3.20	.984	1	5	3.00	3.00	4.00	
ITEM8 BASELINE	1.91	.864	1	4	1.00	2.00	3.00	P<0.001
ITEM8 FOLLOW UP	3.13	.886	1	5	2.00	3.00	4.00	
ITEM9 BASELINE	1.93	.847	1	4	1.00	2.00	3.00	P<0.001
ITEM9 FOLLOW UP	3.14	.931	1	5	3.00	3.00	4.00	
ITEM10 BASELINE	1.89	.729	1	4	1.00	2.00	2.00	P<0.001
ITEM10 FOLLOW UP	3.45	1.035	1	5	3.00	4.00	4.00	
Wilcoxon sign rank test applied								

The table no.19 shows mean quality of life scores for ten items assessed at baseline and follow-up. Scores significantly improved for all items, with baseline means ranging from 1.74 to 2.15 and follow-up means increasing to 3.15 to 3.45. Standard deviations also increased, reflecting greater variability in responses at follow-up. All changes were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Table No.20: The mean quality of life score observed at baseline and at follow-up.

Paired Samples Statistics				
	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Significance
QOL at Baseline	19.7763	152	2.93008	-12.31579 p-value<0.001
QOL at Follow-up	32.0921	152	5.97274	

The table no.20 shows the mean quality of life score improved from 19.78 (SD = 2.93) at baseline to 32.09 (SD = 5.97) at follow-up. This significant change ($p < 0.001$) reflects a substantial enhancement in quality of life.

iv) Correlation between medication adherence and QOL (quality of life)

Table No.21: First follow-up medication adherence observed among different categories of quality of life assessed during follow-up.

First Follow-up MARS Score	QOL AT FOLLOW-UP			Total
	Poor QOL	Moderate QOL	Good QOL	
Poor Adherence	20	26	0	46
	43.5%	56.5%	0.0%	100.0%
Moderate Adherence	5	86	5	96
	5.2%	89.6%	5.2%	100.0%
Good Adherence	0	1	9	10
	0.0%	10.0%	90.0%	100.0%
Total	25	113	14	152
	16.4%	74.3%	9.2%	100.0%

chi-square statistic = 116.757, p-value < 0.001 (significant association)

Table 21 highlight a strong correlation between medication adherence and quality of life (QOL) at the first follow-up. Among poorly adherent patients, 43.5% had poor QOL and 56.5% moderate QOL, while none reported good QOL. In contrast, 90% of those with good adherence reported good QOL, showing that better adherence leads to improved QOL.

Table no.22: Second follow-up medication adherence observed among different categories of quality of life assessed during follow-up

Second Follow-up MARS Score	QOL AT FOLLOW-UP			Total
	Poor QOL	Moderate QOL	Good QOL	
Poor Adherence	17	15	0	32
	53.1%	46.9%	0.0%	100.0%
Moderate Adherence	8	98	11	117
	6.8%	83.8%	9.4%	100.0%
Good Adherence	0	0	3	3
	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Total	25	113	14	152
	16.4%	74.3%	9.2%	100.0%
chi-square statistic = 69.909, p-value < 0.001 (significant association)				

Table 22 from the second follow-up reinforce the link between medication adherence and quality of life (QOL). Among patients with poor adherence, 53.1% had poor QOL and 46.9% had moderate QOL. In the moderate adherence group, 83.8% reported moderate QOL, while 9.4% had good QOL. Notably, all patients with good adherence reported good QOL, confirming that better adherence leads to improved QOL.

Table 23: Third follow-up medication adherence observed among different categories of quality of life assessed during follow-up

Third Follow-up MARS Score	QOL AT FOLLOW-UP			Total
	Poor QOL	Moderate QOL	Good QOL	
Poor Adherence	12	7	0	19
	63.2%	36.8%	0.0%	100.0%
Moderate Adherence	13	103	3	119
	10.9%	86.6%	2.5%	100.0%
Good Adherence	0	3	11	14
	0.0%	21.4%	78.6%	100.0%
Total	25	113	14	152
	16.4%	74.3%	9.2%	100.0%
chi-square statistic = 121.627, p-value < 0.001 (significant association)				

Table 23 from the third follow-up further confirm the link between medication adherence and quality of life (QOL). Among patients with poor adherence, 63.2% reported poor QOL, while 36.8% had moderate QOL. In the moderate adherence group, 86.6% reported moderate QOL, and 2.5% had good QOL. Notably, 78.6% of those with good adherence reported good QOL, reinforcing the connection between higher adherence and better QOL.

Table 24: Fourth follow-up medication adherence observed among different categories of quality of life assessed during follow-up

Fourth Follow-up MARS Score	QOL AT FOLLOW-UP			Total
	Poor QOL	Moderate QOL	Good QOL	
Poor Adherence	2	0	0	2
	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Moderate Adherence	22	84	1	107
	20.6%	78.5%	0.9%	100.0%
Good Adherence	1	29	13	43
	2.3%	67.4%	30.2%	100.0%
Total	25	113	14	152
	16.4%	74.3%	9.2%	100.0%
chi-square statistic = 45.588, p-value < 0.001 (significant association)				

Table 24 from the fourth follow-up show a continued link between medication adherence and quality of life (QOL). All poorly adherent patients reported poor QOL, while 78.5% of those with moderate adherence had moderate QOL. In the good adherence group, 30.2% reported good QOL, further confirming that better adherence leads to improved QOL.

Table No. 25: Panel of Expert Agreement on the items of the PIL

No. of Items	Items	No. in Agreement	Content Validity Index	Percentage (%)
1	H. Pylori infection	6	1	100
2	Causes of h. pylori infection	6	1	100
3	Symptoms of H. pylori	6	1	100
4	Testing for h. pylori	5	0.83	83.33
5	Medication adherence on H. pylori	6	1	100
6	Diet and life style modification	6	1	100

The above table no.25 shows that the frequency and percentage of the items on the participant information leaflet agreed by the experts for the evaluation of the content validity according to Lawshe's scale.

Conclusion

This study evaluated medication adherence and quality of life among patients with H. pylori infection, emphasizing barriers to adherence and the impact of pharmacist-led interventions. Key barriers included the misconception of stopping treatment upon symptom relief (94.1%), side effects (91.4%), and the prolonged treatment duration (88.8%).

Targeted pharmacist-led counseling and lifestyle education significantly improved adherence, reducing non-completion rates from 45.4% to 2.6% over 14 days. Correspondingly, quality of life scores improved from 19.78 to 32.09. A clear association was observed between improved adherence and enhanced patient well-being.

These findings support the integration of pharmacist-led interventions and tailored education into treatment plans. Future research should explore these strategies across diverse settings and assess the role of digital tools in supporting adherence.

Conflict of interest statement

All authors contributed positively to the writing of this manuscript, and there is no conflict of interest as agreed upon in the content of this research.

Statement of ethical approval

Statement of informed consent

The informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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